

should be clearly recognised for the sake of forging community policing partnerships and implementing problem-solving strategies which will necessitate changes in the organisational structure of policing.

Key Words: Community policing, crime prevention, vigilante services and insecurity.

Background to the study

Community policing in Nigeria is a security tactics used as an alternative or complementary effort from the immediate community to support the efforts of police force in fighting crime and criminal activities. As a matter of fact, the police in Nigeria cannot sustain or maintain crime free communities devoid of voluntary local efforts to complement theirs. It is also believed that the people residing in a particular community can effortlessly recognise those people perpetrating evil in their immediate environment and will be easy for them in tracking them down; they have sufficient knowledge of geographical settings of their areas (Olusegun, 2016).

Community policing in Nigeria takes different forms ranging from Community Development Association (CDA); Peace and Security Committee; Landlords and Tenants Security Harmony in which certain able-bodied men in the community are grouped to watch over the community rotationally; Civilian Joint Task Force (in the northern region); Vigilante Service Group and so on (Olusegun, 2016).

In all societies, it is the responsibility of law enforcement agencies and the police in particular to keep law and order, as this is the main purpose for which they are recruited and trained. They are mainly saddled with the obligations of preventing crime and apprehending criminals (Mulugeta & Mekuriaw, 2017). In performing their duties of crime prevention, the police are faced by certain difficulties such as the perception of the public of the police being non-committed and irresponsible, thus affecting their

relationship negatively (Kasali & Odetola, 2016). Solving a crime requires the involvement of the community, without which it will be difficult for the police to successfully prevent or solve problems of crime. Given these challenges, the introduction of community policing became the best alternative to prevent crime or to reduce the rate of same. The justification behind this joint work is the belief that the police alone cannot ensure and maintain security in a community, and in this regard, the concept of community policing was developed (Mulugeta et al, 2017).

Most recently security has been redefined following the awareness by government that security cannot be monopolised locally as well as globally. This consciousness has led to broadening the idea of security to incorporate private participants and civilians in the management of security (Kasali & et al, 2016). Effective community policing is only possible with a level of trust between the police and the community. But, in Nigeria, there is a feeling of distrust between the public and the police, which makes the concept of community policing unrealistic and unachievable. This mistrust stems from the inability of the police to share power with the civilians as they are used to receiving orders from their superiors, as well as the fact that they find it hard to accept another policing model different from the traditional model they have been used to for a very long time (Gbenemene & Adishi, 2017). In view of this, the study examines the roles of community policing on crime prevention in Nigeria, with the study area of Esan land, made up of five Local Government Areas in central senatorial district of Edo State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The palpable tension as a result of insecurity has affected the dignity and quality of life of both individuals and the society. This has portend danger for peace, progress and development of the country. The citizens need peaceful and safe environment to be able to attain their social, economic and political dreams. The

state police whose duty it is to provide security has consistently admitted that it was handicapped because of a combination of factors among which are lack of resources, poor government support and poor condition of services resulting in ill-motivated, ill-equipped and insufficient workforce (NPF Report, 2008).

Recent trend of insecurity in Nigeria where crimes such as kidnap, banditry, insurgency, armed robbery, cultism and other related fraudulent practices are on the increase which constitute sources of worry to major stakeholders and the public at large. The situation is further aggravated by the increasing inability of security agencies especially the police to protect lives and properties. The task of the police in the maintenance of law and order in every society cannot be overlooked. What is of importance to the people is how the police execute their duty of crime prevention and control within society. The Nigeria police have a negative history of public mistrust and maltreatment. The way the people are treated by the police determines the level of cooperation and support they will give to the police. Nigeria as a diverse society requires a police force that will appreciate and work with various segments of the Nigerian society while carrying out their duties of crime prevention and control in the community. The old policing style and training prospectus focused much on fighting crime, rather than preventing crime in partnership with the people (Arisukwu, 2014).

Copious literatures abound on fighting crime rather than preventing it with community participation. The need to fill this gap by taking a step further to examine the roles of community policing on crime prevention in Esan Land, which is made up of five Local Government Areas of the Central Senatorial District of Edo State, Nigeria is the focus of this study through its attempt by using Esan West Local Government Area for study area.

The study aims at examining the roles of community policing on crime prevention in Nigeria, while its specific objectives include; finding out the extent of awareness of

community policing in Nigeria; examine community participation in sensitisation and patrolling in its effort of crime prevention in Nigeria. To achieving the aforementioned objectives, the study seeks to proffer answers to the following research questions:

- i. What is the extent of awareness of community policing in Nigeria?
- ii. Does community participation in identifying crime affect crime prevention?
- iii. Does community participation in sensitization affect crime prevention? and
- iv. To what extent has community participation in patrolling prevented crime?

Conceptual Review

Community policing in Nigeria

Community policing is a model of policing, developed from the idea that the police and the citizens of a community can collaboratively work together creatively to prevent and solve crime related issues, in order to minimise the fear of crime, ensure safety and improve life quality in the community (Amadi, 2014). Prior to the emergence of community policing, police were perceived as professionals charged with the control of crime and restoring order. This implies that the duty of protection and crime prevention was strictly left to the control of the police. However, with the introduction of community policing concept, the perception changed to viewing policing as partnership with citizens in order to maintain order in the society and create a neighbourhood devoid of crime (Amadi, 2014).

Community Police is a kind of cooperation between the community people and police in checking crime and ensuring the general security of citizens (Omoruyi, 2001; Olusegun, 2016). Community policing is, in essence, collaboration between the police and the community to identify and solve community

problems with the police no longer being the sole guardian of law and order, but all members of the community become active allies in the effort to enhance the safety and quality of neighbourhoods. The best panacea to the prevalent problems of kidnapping, abduction, robbery and stealing and even insurgency is community policing, the people in each localities can easily identify evil perpetrators in their localities as the case with Civilian Joint Task Force and the activities of Vigilante Service Group (VSG) in the North Eastern part of Nigeria in which they serve as local guide to the security operatives in apprehending members of the notorious terrorist group (Boko Haram) in the country (Olusegun, 2016).

Abba (2014) pitched tent from his understanding of the tenets of community policing to re-orient the police personnel and re-activate the Nigeria police patrol system. As he puts it, Patrol is the backbone of crime prevention duties. Supporting, Arase (2016) maintained that modern policing and beat patrol strategies have expanded the roles of police beyond the traditional surveillance function of walking the beat alone. This indicates that members of the public would always expect the Nigeria police to provide an active and highly visible presence in the community to reassure the people of providing their safety needs and keeping peace in the community. But, if the fight against Boko haram criminality and terrorism, Fulani herdsmen banditry, kidnapping, ritual and political killings in Nigeria among others is to be achieved through the integration of community-based policing; then, it should be expected that the Nigeria police and the Federal Government would not be in dilemma on how to reform the police to cope with the tensed insecurity across Nigeria. While the Nigeria police continue to receive thrash for its inability to keep peace and maintain security in Nigeria, the colossal killings and wanton destruction of lives and properties are increasing on daily basis.

The movement towards community policing has gained momentum in recent years as police and community leaders search for more effective ways to promote public safety and to enhance the quality of life in their neighbourhoods (Ikuteyijo & Rotimi, 2012). The goal of community policing is to reduce crime and disorder by carefully examining the characteristics of problems in neighbourhoods and then applying appropriate problem-solving remedies. There are compelling reasons why law enforcement leaders believe the time has come to alter the policies and practices of their organisations. These reasons are rooted in the history of policing and police research during the last quarter of a century, in the changing nature of communities, and in the shifting characteristics of crime and violence that affect these communities.

Tilley (2012) argues that, in this rapidly changing environment where police cope with an epidemic drug problem, gang activity, and increased levels of violence among youths, the concept of community policing is taking hold. Police leaders using this common-sense approach to the problems of crime and disorder, an approach that may very well enhance and maximise performance and resources, have struck a responsive chord in both national and local governments level, communities across the Nation. Government and community leaders are beginning to recognise that they also must accept responsibility for keeping their neighbourhoods safe. Communities must take a unified stand against crime, violence, and disregard for the law, and must make a commitment to increasing crime prevention and intervention activities. Police agencies must help build stronger, more self-sufficient communities in which crime and disorder will not thrive.

Altruistically, community policing faces myriads of challenges in Nigeria. In other words, numerous efforts by various police administrations to curtail the level of crime in Nigeria, and crime and social disorder still persist in the country (Ndukwe, 2018). Thousands of lives and millions of naira worth of

properties have been lost as a result of one crime or the other. Some believed that the inability of the Nigerian police to ensure maximum security in the country is as a result of so many social and technical constraints, among which are lack of equipment and sour relationship between the police and public (Incardi, 2007), while others believe that it is due to Institutional Constraints (Tierney, 2006); Corruption (Eke, 2009); Godfatherism (Alemika & Chukwuma, 2000); Poor Welfare Services (Incardi, 2007); and Loss of Public Confidence.

The police and community participation

Nwanguma (2012) documented that the official integration of community policing model in Nigeria police system was launched by the Federal Government on 27th April, 2004 in which Enugu State Police Command was used as trial. The evaluation report of the trial showed that within the period, Enugu State had impressive reduction in quite numbers of cases. Some of these cases are affray, burglary, murder, stealing, rape, bank robbery, highway robbery, human-trafficking, communal clash or tribal crisis among others. It also showed tremendous improvement on the mundane relationship between the police and members of the community. As Nwanguma (2012) rightly puts it, “the outcome encouraged the police authority to include other eleven state police commands, which included Benue, Kano, Osun, Borno, Ogun, Abia, Anambra, Kaduna, Nasarawa, Edo and Rivers that had history of high rates of crime.” According to Nigeria Police Force Report (2011), integration of community policing has not only assisted to reduce the threats associated with the rising crime and disorder in all the pilot state police commands including reduction in the daily occurrences of Boko haram terrorism, Fulani herdsmen, banditry, and other serious crimes in Benue, Borno, and Kano states; it has helped to reduce the rampant incidences of kidnapping, bank robbery, and other heinous crimes cases in Osun, Edo, Ogun, and Rivers states. Beyond this,

Nwanguma (2012) observed significance reduction of reported cases of police extortions, and extra-judicial killings. Emphasising the efficacy of the police-public teamwork.

Alemika (2012) argued that the changing nature of communities and the shifting characteristics of crime like kidnapping for ransom, bank robbery, terrorism, corruption, ritual killings, and child-stealing among other violent crimes and public disorders are compelling reasons why the philosophy of community engagement in police system should not be ignored in Nigeria. This is also in tandem with what was observed in Bureau of Justice Assistance (1994) that innovative practice in which people are made to participate in policing within their localities will assist in curbing the eruption of violent-crimes and insecurity within many communities.

Dawodu, (2007) supported the above views when he said that “effective and efficient policing need the co-operation of the public within which the police operate. It is probably, in this sense that Abba as quoted in the Nigeria Police Force Order (2014) issued the celebrated “Force Order 464” to re-educate the Nigeria police personnel on the need to focus on patrol activities as one of the primary police functions for effective crime prevention; familiarising themselves with members of the public; rebuilding public confidence and trust in them; and fostering community co-operation with the police among others. Arase (2018) said there is no debate about the efficacy of community policing model for keeping peace and providing safety; security management and control. As he said, even among police personnel themselves, research carried out in 14 states discovered that if community policing strategy is adopted, it could assist to eradicate most of the challenges attributed to the traditional reactive police culture. Yakubu (2019) equally documented that at the 11th National Development Submit of Traditional Rulers held in the Shehu Musa Yar’Adua Centre, Abuja held on 15th October, 2019, the Vice President of Nigeria Professor Yemi Osinbajo said that a

meticulous implementation of community policing would reduce internal insecurity and bring about peace and harmonious co-existence among Nigerians across the country. This simply suggests that the integration of community policing into the Nigeria police force by the Federal Government on 27th April, 2004 has implementation challenge.

Not contradicting the usefulness of community policing in Nigeria police system, Dandison (2007) held that police methods and technologies, such as motorized patrols and the use of rapid crime response techniques created greater rift between the police and members of the community. As he saw it, because the police officers no longer patrol their beats, they have difficulty to know the neighbourhood residents they are meant to serve and protect. This made the police to have less awareness and involvement in the problem of the community they serve.

Under community policing the relationship between citizens and the police is supposed to improve if they are to curb crime. It does appear that increased cooperation between the police and local residents increases satisfaction with police services on both sides, although this is not universal. In a study done in St. Petersburg, Florida, 85 per cent of those residents who lived in community policing areas of the city reported being very or somewhat satisfied with their neighbourhood police services.

Community policing promises that closer alliances between the police and the community will help reduce citizen fear of crime, improve police-community relations, and facilitate more effective responses to community problems. But there are also drawbacks associated with community policing including hostility between the police and neighbourhood residents, which can hinder productive partnerships, increases in officers' decision-making autonomy, can lead to greater opportunities for police corruption and resistance within the police organisation and can hamper community policing successful implementation (Wong, 2009).

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical foundation for this study is based on the Broken Windows Theory (BWT) and the functionalist theory. The broken window theory suggests that lawlessness grows in a society when societies begin to tolerate relatively minor violations of public order and deliberate efforts needed to crack down on this menace are not in place. Formulated within the wider context of the social structural theory of community policing, particularly the social disorganisation theory, broken window theory argues that there is a direct relationship between higher rates of deviance and the increased complexities of urban life, that disorder and crime are linked in a developmental sequence.

Introduced by Wilson and Kelling in 1982, the theory emphasizes that the police and the criminal justice system alone cannot carry the heavy burden of security hence, the need to involve the community (Olusegun, 2016). If crimes are the result of social disorganisation, then the police departments should work to improve social control by strengthening community ties and encourage behaviours that will provide the basis for regulating individual conducts within the society. This approach to community policing requires that citizens assume the responsibility of controlling crime by reporting any deviant behaviour promptly to the police and also by cooperating as witnesses when the crime occurs. Lombardo and Lough (2007) further argued that this approach to crime prevention will allow community policing programme increase the informal social control mechanisms inherent in communities which had in the past been lost to crimes and disorders. Policing is one of the major formal devices designed to bring about the regulation and control of behaviour in a community. If social disapproval and other informal social processes fail to contain crime, abuse and sociopathic behaviour, the police are then expected to provide a main line of defence against deviants and lawbreakers.

The *Functionalist Theory* on the other hand posits that behaviour in society is structured and relationships between members of society are organised in terms of rules and that social relationships are patterned and recurrent. Functionalists believe that there are values in consensus and a high degree of consensus binds members together to form an integrated and cohesive unit. The theory assumes that a certain degree of order and stability is necessary for the survival of social system. Functionalists downplay the conflict in society between classes and believe that once norms and values are maintained, the society would be conflict free. Developed by Emile Durkheim and Talcott Parsons in the twentieth century, functionalism looks at society as a set of interrelated parts which together forms a whole. It considers society as a structural system made up of interrelated parts. The social system has certain basic needs that must be met if it is to survive. These needs are known as functional prerequisites. This means that each part, will in some ways, affect every other part and the system as a whole. It also follows that the survival of the system depends on the compatibility of the various parts. Since the Nigeria Police is an integral part of the Nigeria social system, its ineffectiveness and poor job performance have implications on the overall security of the society. Other agencies that provide security becomes impacted as a result of the inability of the police to perform its function effectively (Inyang & Abraham 2007; Gbenemene & Adishi, 2017; Audu, 2016). However, in situations where everyone plays his part in the social system, peace and stability is inevitable (Ordu & Nnam, 2017).

Empirical Review

Akinyemi (2021) carried out a study on the implications of community policing for national peace and security in Nigeria using a systematic review of literature. It was observed that in Nigeria, community policing has been adopted only in principle and has not been implemented or practiced. Also, the level of trust

and partnership that is required between the police and members of the public is yet to be achieved as the challenges confronting the security framework of the country have not been addressed. Ngwu and Ahuruonye (2017) studied the concept of community policing and its effectiveness in maintaining order, preventing crime and reducing fear in communities as opposed to the traditional concentration on execution of serious street crimes founded on “jungle justice”. Secondary source of data from the existing literature were utilized as well as books, journal articles and the Focus Group Discussion (FGD). It was revealed that police attitude resulted in lack of co-operation of the public with the police and also in giving the police information on the situation of crime in their individual communities. Notwithstanding these limitations, community policing is crucial in maintaining a safe and crime-free society in Nigeria. Olusegun (2016) examined the different views of community policing in south-west Nigeria through the consultation of related textbooks, publications and journals which revealed that the perception of the police and the community retain the fact that the police force alone cannot successfully tackle crimes in the society given their apparent inadequacies without adequate backing of the members of the community.

Braimah and Masajuma (2021) studied policing through the community as a strategy of strengthening the security architecture of Nigeria, adopted a variety of theories such as citizen participation and the broken window to interrogate the subject matter. The study x-rayed some empirical studies on the perception of the Nigeria police by the public and also contextualized citizens’ participation in community policing to situate the effectiveness of policing through the community. The study found out that policing through the community will improve intelligence gathering capacity of the security agencies in its fight against criminality and insurgencies in Nigeria. The study recommends that the present structure of the police should be

decentralized and also take measures to reinvent it to change the negative perception of the public towards it. Oikhala (2021) examined the effects of community policing on police statutory functions in Nigeria. Data were collected from relevant textbooks, journals, newspapers and other official records. The data congregated were analysed through descriptive method. Espousing the broken window theory as theoretical framework, community policing is considered as a proactive crime and disorder reducing strategy as against the 'pursue and catch' reactive oriented. The paper found community policing as helpful to curbing internal security threats in Nigeria. It argued that the effectiveness of community policing is overturned by gamut of the police different operational agenda; inconsistency in policy; and resistance from some officers and rank and files. The paper recommended that the police statutory functions of curbing insecurity in Nigeria would remain a daydream without active community policing.

Finally, Twesigye, Mamerito, Shamusu, and Wafula (2022), investigated the relationship between Community Policing and Crime Prevention in Kampala Central Division, taken a case of Central Division. Specifically, the study investigated community participation in identifying crimes, sensitisation about crimes and how patrolling affects crime reduction. The study adopted a case study of Kampala Division and utilised a sample of 120 respondents selected using purposive and simple random sampling techniques. Data was collected using questionnaires and interviews guides. Quantitative Data was analysed using correlation and multiple regression to establish the relationship between community policing and crime prevention. The study findings revealed criminal preventions was significantly related with community participation in identifying crimes, sensitization of crimes as well as patrolling and crime reduction in Kampala central division. The study concluded that community policing contributes to crime prevention in Kampala central division. The

study recommended the need to improve management practices in community policing.

Research Design

The selection of a research design is informed by the research questions and objectives (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2000). This study adopted a combination of descriptive and quantitative design.

The population of the study is the totality of the objects or elements being studied and to which the conclusions or generalisations of our result will apply. This study focuses on the roles of community policing on crime prevention in Nigeria, with particular focus on Esan Land. The population of study therefore, consists of the totality of 188,700 residents in Esan West Local Government, Edo State; sourced from National Population Commission of Nigeria (web) and National Bureau of Statistics (2022).

A sample size of 201 respondents was carefully selected through random sampling techniques. On this basis, the Questionnaires were distributed in the major communities in Esan West Local Government Area.

The instrument that was used for data collection in this study is a questionnaire and an unstructured interview. The 29—item questionnaire was divided into three (3) parts: Section “a” was a covering letter, section “b” captured respondents selected demographic and socio-economic characteristics such as gender, occupation, age, educational qualification, occupation and income. Section “c” contained items measuring awareness of community policing on crime prevention in Nigeria.

To satisfy content validity, a careful definition of various variables as well as scale was used. The instrument was evaluated as to how well it meets the standard. This helped in making certain that the instrument indeed factored in the entire content

area of the study. With respect to reliability of the instrument, the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 20.0) was used to ascertain internal consistency as demonstrated by Cronbach’s Alpha values.

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 20.0) was used for all the analyses. All tests were carried out at the 5% level of statistical significance.

Crime prevention is the dependent variable in this study while the independent/explanatory variables include community participation in identifying crime, community participation in sensitisation and community participation in patrolling.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of community participation in identifying crime and crime prevention

	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Unsure	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean
1.	Community participation in identifying crimes helps in taking protective measures against it	106 (52.7%)	79 (39.3%)	11 (5.5%)	2 (1.0%)	3 (1.5%)	4.4080
2.	Community partnerships in crime identification help to know crime spots	89 (44.3%)	54 (26.4%)	12 (6.0%)	34 (16.9%)	13 (6.5%)	3.8507
3.	Community participation helps in reporting of crimes where they prevail	92 (45.8%)	79 (49.3%)	11 (5.5%)	16 (8.0%)	3 (1.5%)	4.1990
4.	Partnerships help in crime prevention in the communities	60 (29.9%)	91 (45.3%)	9 (4.5%)	27 (13.4%)	14 (7.0%)	3.7761
5.	Participation promotes primary crime prevention responses	25 (12.4%)	54 (26.9%)	14 (7.0%)	40 (19.9%)	68 (33.8%)	2.6418
Overall mean for community participation in identifying crime and crime prevention							3.7751

Source: Author’s field work (2024).

The result in *Table 1* above, while the finding is that majority of the respondents disagreed that “participation promotes primary crime prevention responses”. The mean value for “participation promotes primary crime

prevention responses” is 2.6418. The overall mean value for participation promotes primary crime prevention responses is 3.7751.

Table 2: Community Participation in Sensitisation and Crime Prevention

	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Unsure	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean
1	Community participation helps in crime identification	24 (11.9%)	60 (29.9%)	15 (7.5%)	60 (29.9%)	42 (20.9%)	2.8209
2	Community participations ensure effective crime mitigation once the community embraces the activities	57 (28.4%)	99 (49.3%)	29 (14.4%)	7 (3.5%)	9 (4.5%)	3.9353
3	Participation ensures effective coordination with the community	71 (35.3%)	115 (57.2%)	9 (4.5%)	3 (1.5%)	3 (1.5%)	4.2338
4	There is effective supervision of the whole process of community policing	37 (18.4%)	58 (28.9%)	20 (10.9%)	42 (20.9%)	32 (15.9%)	3.1376
5	Public participation makes the concerned entities to effectively monitor the policing process	26 (12.9%)	116 (57.7%)	28 (13.9%)	22 (10.9%)	9 (4.5%)	3.6368
6	Collaboration enhances exchange of information on violence prevention	53 (26.4%)	116 (57.7%)	14 (7.0%)	10 (5.0%)	8 (4.5%)	3.9751
7	The strategy creates, implements and monitors a national action plan for crime prevention	55 (27.4%)	68 (33.8%)	57 (28.4%)	11 (5.5%)	10 (5.0%)	3.7313
8	Community participation also enhances capacity for collecting data on violence	25 (12.4%)	90 (44.8%)	43 (21.4%)	26 (12.9%)	17 (8.5%)	3.3980
	Overall mean for community participation in sensitization and crime prevention						3.6086

Source: Author’s field work (2024).

The result in *Table 2* speaks for its self and the rest of the questions/statements measuring community participation in sensitisation and crime prevention are above the

average bench mark of 3 as shown in Table 2. The overall mean for community participation in sensitization and crime prevention is 3.6086

Table 3: Community participation in patrolling and crime prevention

S/N	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Unsure	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean
21	Participation strategy ensures effective problem identification	48 (23.9%)	91 (45.3%)	31 (15.4%)	22 (10.9%)	9 (4.5%)	3.7313
22	Community participation in patrolling and crime prevention strategy also enables the community to carry out problem evaluation	57 (28.4%)	96 (47.8%)	36 (17.9%)	7 (3.5%)	5 (2.5%)	3.9602
23	Participation in patrolling and crime prevention also helps the community in prioritizing problems	37 (18.4%)	85 (42.3%)	42 (20.9%)	23 (11.4%)	14 (7.0%)	3.5373
24	Community participation in patrolling and crime prevention strategy ensures effective research about the problems	41 (20.4%)	80 (39.8%)	58 (28.9%)	16 (8.0%)	6 (3.0%)	3.6667
25	It is also a stepping stone to developing solutions to problems	66 (32.8%)	102 (50.7%)	22 (10.9%)	8 (4.0%)	3 (1.5%)	4.0945
26	It also helps in evaluating the success of the responses	50 (24.9%)	104 (51.7%)	38 (18.9%)	6 (3.0%)	3 (1.5%)	3.9552
Overall mean for community participation in patrolling and crime prevention							3.8242

Source: Author’s field work (2024).

The result in Table 3 as above and the rest of the questions/statements measuring community participation in patrolling and crime prevention, is above the average bench mark of 3. Their average scores range from 3.6667 to 4.0945. The overall mean value for community participation in patrolling and crime prevention is 3.8242.

Table 4: Crime Prevention Strategies

	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Unsure	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean
	Door-to-door contacts is used as a crime prevention strategy	42 (20.9%)	60 (29.9%)	24 (11.9%)	46 (22.9%)	29 (14.4%)	3.1990
	Community members are encouraged to share intelligence with the police.	60 (29.9%)	101 (50.2%)	16 (8.0%)	11 (5.5%)	13 (6.5%)	3.9154
	Community members are provided with hotlines to report crime related incidences or signs	74 (36.8%)	78 (38.8%)	17 (8.5%)	10 (5.0%)	12 (6.0%)	4.0052
	Police patrols are easily accessible, visible and familiar to their community.	34 (16.9%)	59 (20.4%)	10 (5.0%)	52 (25.9%)	36 (17.9%)	3.0157
	Overall mean for community participation in patrolling and crime prevention						3.8242

Source: Author’s field work (2024).

The result in Table 4 as above and the overall mean value for community participation in patrolling and crime prevention is 3.8242.

Discussion of the Research Findings

Effect of community policing on crime prevention in Nigeria was examined in this study. The study found that preponderance of respondents is aware of community policing in their community with 93.0% of the total respondents indicating that they are aware of community policing in their locality. The study also found that there is no significant relationship between community participation in identifying crime; community participation in community patrolling and crime prevention in Nigeria. The findings in this regard contradicts the findings by Twesigye et al

(2022) who reported that crime prevention in Kampala Central Division had a significant relationship with community participation in identifying crimes and community participation in community patrolling.

Similarly, this study found that there is a significant relationship between crime prevention in Nigeria and community participation in sensitisation on crime prevention. The result contradicts the findings by Twesigye, et al. (2022) who found that there is no significant relationship between crime prevention and community participation in sensitisation on crime prevention. More so, findings showed that public participation in sensitisation makes the concerned entities to effectively monitor the policing process which means that there is increased collaboration and exchange of information on crime prevention in communities. This is in agreement with Sousa and Kelling (2006) who noted that crime prevention in society must be a collaborative effort between the communities and the police since this involves exchange of vital information regarding how crime can be prevented. The finding implies that collaborative effort during community sensitisation about crime plays a significant role in crime reduction in communities heavily affected by crime.

Summary of Research Findings

The findings of the study are as follows:

- i. Majority of respondents is aware of community policing in their community.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between crime prevention and community participation in identifying crime.
- iii. There is a significant relationship between crime prevention and community participation in sensitization on crime prevention.
- iv. There is no significant relationship between crime prevention and community participation in community patrolling.

Conclusion

The study has attempted to find out the effect of community policing on crime prevention in Nigeria. The results indicate that greater number of respondents is aware of community policing in their community. The study found that there is no significant relationship between crime prevention and community participation in identifying crime and community participation in community patrolling. Finally, the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between crime prevention and community participation in sensitisation on crime prevention.

Recommendations

The research findings from this study no doubt have far-reaching implications for community policing in Nigeria. The study recommends as follows:

- i. The need to improve management practices in community policing.
- ii. That change management requires a clear recognition that forging community policing partnerships and implementing problem-solving activities will necessitate changes in the organisational structure of policing.
- iii. Community policing needs to allow law enforcement to get back to the principles upon which it was founded, to integrate itself once again into the fabric of the community so that the people come to the police for counsel and help before a serious problem arises, not after the fact.

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RE-INVIGORATING THE TEACHING AND LEARNING OF GUIDANCE AND COUNSELING IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract

The teaching and development of a child can only take place in an environment conducive for teaching and learning. It is in realization of the above that all educational services which can promote teaching and learning in schools are given prominent attention by educational planners. Counselling services in school develop asses and improve educational programmes, enhance teaching and improve the competence of the teacher and reduce cost for the children. Therefore, this paper aims at the need for effective counselling services in secondary schools. Consequently, this paper seeks to examine the concept of counselling, the different counselling services like educational, vocational and socio/personal services, the various problems facing guidance and counselling as it affects teaching and learning in Secondary schools. Finally, the paper recommended among others that individuals be made to understand appreciate and accept guidance and counselling services in secondary schools because of the roles they play in effective teaching and learning process.

Keywords: Guidance and counselling, teaching, learning, school guidance counsellors'